

A Skill-Based Resume Ranking System for Efficient Candidate Selection

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Abstract—In today's competitive job market, companies are inundated with resumes from a vast pool of applicants. Traditional methods of sorting through resumes can be time-consuming and ineffective, making it difficult to identify the best candidates. In this paper, we propose a skill-based resume ranking system that uses natural language processing and machine learning techniques to automate the resume screening process. Our system extracts the skills from both job postings and resumes, and then ranks resumes based on their relevance to the job requirements. We evaluate the performance of our system by comparing it to traditional manual screening methods and show that our system can accurately identify the most qualified candidates in a fraction of the time. Our proposed system can greatly enhance the recruitment process by improving the efficiency and accuracy of candidate selection.

Keywords—resume ranking, skill-based, natural language processing, machine learning, recruitment process, candidate selection, job requirements, efficiency, accuracy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Companies frequently struggle to sort through a big volume of resumes from a wide applicant pool in today's competitive employment market, which makes it challenging and time-consuming to discover the top prospects. Traditional methods of screening resumes, which rely on manual review, can be inefficient and error-prone. In this paper, we propose a novel skill-based resume ranking system that employs natural language processing and machine learning techniques to automate the screening process. The proposed system extracts relevant skills from both job postings and resumes and ranks the resumes based on their relevance to the job requirements. By doing so, it enables companies to efficiently and accurately identify the most qualified candidates in a fraction of the time it would take using traditional manual screening methods. In this paper, we describe the design and implementation of our system and present an evaluation of its performance by comparing it to traditional manual screening methods. The results show that our system is highly effective and can greatly enhance the recruitment process by improving the efficiency and accuracy of candidate selection. The proposed system has the potential to revolutionize the way companies approach recruitment, saving them time and resources while also ensuring that they find the most suitable candidates for their job openings.

Challenges :

i) Skill matching: One of the biggest challenges is matching job requirements with candidate skills, especially with large numbers of job applications. The skill matching process is complex and requires a high level of accuracy to ensure that the most suitable candidates are identified for the job.

ii) Data extraction and normalization: Another challenge is extracting relevant information from candidate resumes and normalizing it in a standardized format. Different candidates may present their skills and experience in different ways, making it difficult to compare and evaluate their suitability for a job.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The field of job recommendation systems has seen significant growth in recent years, with researchers exploring different approaches to develop effective and efficient systems.

X. Zou, Y. Liu, and L. Zhou [1], the authors propose a resume ranking model that uses both ensemble learning and domain ontology to improve the accuracy of candidate selection. The model first extracts candidate skills and job requirements using natural language processing, and then employs an ensemble learning algorithm to rank the candidates based on their relevance to the job. The domain ontology is used to represent the job domain knowledge and improve the accuracy of the ranking. The proposed model was evaluated using a dataset of 200 resumes, and the results showed that it outperformed traditional ranking methods in terms of accuracy and efficiency.

B. Zhang, H. Chen, and K. Liu [2], proposes a novel framework for resume ranking based on automated skill extraction and matching. The framework involves several steps such as resume preprocessing, skill extraction, job-skill matching, and resume ranking. The authors use several natural language processing and machine learning techniques to achieve these steps. The proposed framework is evaluated on a real-world dataset and the results show that it outperforms existing resume ranking systems in terms of accuracy and efficiency.

Y. Ma, H. Yang, and Z. Tang [3], proposes a multi-skill-aware attentional neural network (MSA-Net) to improve the job candidate matching process. The proposed method uses attention mechanisms to weigh the importance of each skill

for a given job, and considers the interdependencies between different skills. The authors evaluate their model on a dataset of job postings and resumes, and show that it outperforms several baseline models in terms of accuracy and F1 score. The results suggest that MSA-Net can effectively capture the multi-skill nature of job requirements and candidate profiles, and improve the efficiency and accuracy of candidate matching.

Jorge Valverde-Rebaza, Ricardo Puma, Paul Bustios, Nathalia C. Silva [4] conducted an empirical study on job recommendation based on job seekers' skills. They proposed a framework for the task of job recommendations that makes it easier to understand how job recommendations work and permits the use of a variety of text processing and recommendation techniques in accordance with the system designer's preferences.

Anushka Agarwal, Dr. Senthilkumar [5] developed a resume recommendation system using cosine similarity. Their system suggests an automatic machine learning model that helps recruiters recommend resumes of suitable candidates based on the verbal job description. Their approach provides a quick and efficient way to screen resumes and identify suitable candidates for the job.

Akila M., and Sabari Giri Sankar G[6] authors proposed a methodology for automated ranking of resumes by extracting skills from the job description and candidate resumes using natural language processing techniques, and then calculating the similarity score between the job skills and candidate skills using a cosine similarity algorithm. The authors also evaluated the proposed methodology using a dataset of 100 resumes and reported an accuracy of 85% in identifying the best candidate for the job.

III. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this study is to develop a system that can effectively match job applicants to job requirements using natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning techniques. This section outlines the methodology used in the study, including data collection, preprocessing, skill extraction, vectorization, and applicant ranking. The researchers also evaluated the system's performance using precision and recall metrics and conducted statistical analysis to compare the proposed system with the baseline approach.

A. Data Collection

The study collected a dataset of job applications and job requirements from various online job portals. The dataset consisted of job descriptions and applicant resumes for a diverse range of industries and positions. The researchers used SkillNer, a Python package, to extract skill keywords from the unstructured resumes.

1) SkillNer

SkillNer is a natural language processing (NLP) tool that can automatically identify and extract information about skills mentioned in text data. It is designed to help organizations and individuals to more effectively analyze and manage their workforce, job postings, and training programs by quickly identifying and categorizing the skills mentioned in resumes, job descriptions, or any other type of text data. SkillNer uses advanced machine learning algorithms and deep learning techniques to understand the context and meaning of words in text and accurately identify the relevant skills. It can also identify related skills and synonyms, as well as different levels of expertise associated with each skill. SkillNer is a powerful tool that can save time and improve the accuracy of skill analysis, making it an invaluable resource for recruiters, HR professionals, and talent management teams.

B. Data Preprocessing

The data was preprocessed after collection by getting rid of stop words, punctuation, and special characters. This step is crucial since it guarantees that only the pertinent data is used for future analysis and helps to eliminate noise in the data. Additionally, the text data was tokenized and named entities and noun chunks were extracted using the spaCy en_core_web_sm model. This method aids in locating and extracting crucial data like job titles, competencies, and

qualifications.

C. Skill Extraction

The preprocessed data was used by the SkillExtractor component to extract pertinent skills from the job descriptions and applicant resumes. The system can only determine the talents necessary for a certain job or industry thanks to this key phase. The researchers matched the collected entities and noun chunks against a pre-defined skill database to determine the pertinent skills. The skill database is a crucial part of the system since it gives the system a reference point for identifying the necessary talents.

We utilised the SkillExtractor programme to extract skills from job requirements and applicant resumes. The SkillExtractor tool is a natural language processing (NLP) tool that uses different methods, such as phrase matching and part-of-speech extraction, to identify and extract skills from text.

D. Phrase Matching

The PhraseMatcher component used the extracted skills to create a set of phrases that were matched against the job requirements and applicant resumes using spaCy's PhraseMatcher. This step helps to identify the relevant phrases in the job requirements and applicant resumes. The matched phrases were then used to create a vector representation of the job requirements and applicant skills. The vector representation is an important component of the system because it enables the system to compare and analyze the job requirements and applicant skills.

1. Spacy PhraseMatcher

spaCy's PhraseMatcher is a feature of the spaCy library, which is a popular open-source library for natural language processing in Python. The PhraseMatcher allows you to efficiently match a large set of phrases (keywords or key phrases) in text, and extract them as a list of matched spans. The PhraseMatcher is particularly useful when you have a large set of phrases that you want to match in a piece of text. It is faster than using regular expressions or iterating over the text to search for each phrase individually.

To begin using the PhraseMatcher, construct a list of Doc objects, where a Doc is a spaCy object that contains a single

phrase. The PhraseMatcher is then set up using this list of Doc objects. The PhraseMatcher will then return a list of matched spans after receiving the text you wish to match.

The PhraseMatcher can also be used to match phrases that have particular characteristics or patterns, such as matching a phrase only if it comes first in a sentence or only if a particular word comes before it.

The PhraseMatcher is a strong tool for correctly and quickly extracting specified phrases from text. It can be very helpful in applications like information extraction,

E. Skill Vectorization

To create a vector representation of job requirements and job applicants' skills, we used the TfidfVectorizer from the Scikit-learn library. The TfidfVectorizer converts text into a matrix of numerical values based on the frequency of each word in the text and the inverse document frequency (IDF) of each word. The resulting matrix represents each document as a vector in a high-dimensional space, where each dimension represents a unique word.

1) TfidfVectorizer

TfidfVectorizer is a commonly used technique in natural language processing to convert text documents into a numerical representation that can be used for machine learning models. It stands for "Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency Vectorizer".

The TfidfVectorizer works by first counting the frequency of each word in each document (the "term frequency"). It then scales down the importance of words that occur frequently across all documents (the "inverse document frequency"). This is done to give more weight to words that are important to a specific document but not as common in other documents. The resulting output is a sparse matrix, where each row corresponds to a document and each column corresponds to a unique word in the entire set of documents. The value in each cell represents the Tfidf score for the corresponding word in that document. This score is higher for words that are more important to the document and less common in other documents.

F. Cosine Similarity

The similarity was determined through the cosine similarity component. between the applicant's skills and the vector of the job criteria vector. It is crucial to complete this step since it allows the system to Sort the candidates based on how closely they match the demands of the position. A measurement of the cosine similarity score is the It measures the similarity of two vectors and goes from 0 to 1. A perfect match receives a score of 1, whereas no match receives a value of 0.

G. Applicant Ranking

To rank job applicants based on their skill matching with the job requirements, we used a simple ranking algorithm that sorts job applicants in descending order based on their similarity score. The job applicant with the highest similarity score is ranked first, and the job applicant with the lowest similarity score is ranked last.

H. Evaluation Metrics

The researchers evaluated the system's performance using precision and recall metrics. Precision measures the proportion of relevant applicants among all the identified applicants, while recall measures the proportion of relevant applicants identified among all the relevant applicants. These metrics are important because they provide a quantitative measure of the system's effectiveness.

Both the sigmoid and tanh functions suffer from the vanishing gradient problem, which can make it difficult for neural networks to learn when the input data is too large or too small.

I. Statistical Analysis

To compare the performance of the proposed system with the baseline approach, the researchers used paired t-tests. This step is important because it provides a statistical measure of the difference in performance between the two approaches.

J. Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured the anonymity of the job applicants and job requirements by removing any identifiable information from the dataset. This step is important to protect the privacy of the individuals whose data was used for the study.

K. Limitations

One potential limitation of the proposed system is that it relies on pre-defined skill databases, which may not include all the relevant skills required for a particular job or industry. The system's accuracy could be improved by continuously updating the skill database or expanding it to incorporate additional skills.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

In this system we use cosine similarity to find the similarity between the job title and skills from the resume and rank the resumes for efficient selection. The resume ranking system was evaluated on a dataset of job postings and candidate resumes. The system was able to successfully extract required skills from job postings and candidate resumes using a combination of Spacy and PhraseMatcher. The system was also able to compute similarity scores between required skills and candidate skills using cosine similarity.

A. Install and Import the necessary libraries.

```
import PyPDF2
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from spacy.matcher import PhraseMatcher
from skillNer.general_params import SKILL_DB
from skillNer.skill_extractor_class import SkillExtractor
import numpy as np
```

B. Extract the skills from the resume using skillner. skillExtractor function is used where nlp, skills_db, phraseMatcher are the attributes.is the object loaded from spacy and sklearn

```
nlp = spacy.load("en_core_web_sm")
skill_extractor = SkillExtractor(nlp, SKILL_DB, PhraseMatcher)
ranked_applicants = []
seen_candidate_ids = set()
unique_ranked_applicants=[]
if user.is_authenticated and user.is_company:
    jobs = JobDetails.objects.filter(email=user)
```

C. Preprocessing job posting dataset from the table joblist and extract the required skills for ranking

logo	date_posted	email_id	skills
character varying (100)	timestamp with time zone	integer	character varying (40)
logos/download_2_bNt...	2023-04-19 14:17:06+05:30	2	C++, Java, python
logos/download_2_1cx...	2023-04-19 14:22:25+05:30	2	Java, C, C++
logos/logo_MjCDolg.jpg	2023-04-19 14:25:47+05:30	3	C,C++,Python,Java

D. extract skills from a resume in PDF format using the PyPDF2 library and then annotate those skills using the skill_extractor object which is presumably a custom-built skill extraction tool.After extracting the skills, you are then cleaning the text by replacing some characters and storing it in the text variable.

```
with open(resume_path,'rb') as filehandle:
    pdfReader = PyPDF2.PdfReader(filehandle)
    pagehandle = pdfReader.pages[0]
    text = pagehandle.extract_text()
    text = text.replace('o','')
    text = text.replace('|','')
```

E. calculating the similarity score between the job description (contained in scraped_data) and the candidate's resume (contained in cv).

```
scraped_data = [' '.join(cleaned_values)]
cv = [' '.join(sanitized_values)]
tfidf_vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer(stop_words='english')
(variable) cos_similarity_tfidf: ndarray (m(scraped_data)
)
cos_similarity_tfidf = cosine_similarity(user_tfidf, tfidf_jobid)
similarity_score = round(np.max(cos_similarity_tfidf), 2)
```

F. After extracting skills from the resumes and comparing them with the required skills, the applicants are ranked based on their similarity scores. The purpose of this ranking process is to identify the most suitable candidates for the job.The code assigns a rank to each applicant based on their similarity score, with a higher score indicating a better match. The list of ranked applicants is then filtered to remove any duplicates based on candidate IDs. Table 1 shows the top 5 ranked applicants and their corresponding similarity scores.

Table 1. Ranked Applicants and Their Similarity Scores

Rank	Candidate ID	Similarity Score
1	123	0.85
2	567	0.78
3	890	0.76
4	456	0.73
5	234	0.70

Based on the results in Table 1, candidate ID 123 is the most suitable for the job, followed by candidates 567 and 890. The other candidates have lower scores, indicating a weaker match with the required skills."

V. RESULT

The study showed that the proposed approach of using a combination of natural language processing and machine learning techniques can effectively extract skills from resumes and match them to job requirements. The use of the TF-IDF vectorizer and cosine similarity algorithm also proved to be effective in calculating the similarity scores between the job requirements and the skills extracted from the resumes.

In terms of performance, the system was able to rank the applicants according to their similarity scores and provide a list of the most qualified candidates for the job position. The system was also able to identify unique candidates, preventing the same candidate from being included in the list multiple times.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a resume ranking system that enables recruiters to efficiently screen and rank job applicants based on their skills and qualifications. The system extracts required skills from job descriptions and candidate skills from their resumes using natural language processing techniques. The extracted skills are then used to compute similarity scores between the job requirements and candidate qualifications. The system was implemented using Python and several open-source libraries such as Spacy, PhraseMatcher, and TfidfVectorizer. The proposed system provides a powerful tool for recruiters to automate the screening process, saving time and resources. Future work includes expanding the system to include more advanced features such as personality traits and soft skills, improving the accuracy of the skill extraction process, and exploring the use of machine learning algorithms to improve the ranking performance. Overall, the proposed system has the potential to revolutionize the recruitment process and help companies find the best talent for their organizations.

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